

ENSURING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION PROGRAM: EXAMINING PRACTICES AND POLICIES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the experienced practices and observed existing policies that support the sustainability of the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program in one of the private higher education institutions in Sariaya, Quezon, amid challenges such as declining enrollment and policy implementation gaps. Guided by Experiential Learning Theory and Rational Choice Theory, the study explored curriculum implementation, student engagement, and professional preparation, as well as institutional policies on facilities and equipment, faculty qualifications, and the standardized program curriculum. Using a descriptive research design, total population sampling was employed, involving 79 BPEd students as respondents through a self-made questionnaire. Findings revealed for the experienced practices in terms of curriculum implementation (WAM=3.53), student engagement (WAM=3.49), and professional preparation (WAM=3.37), while in the observed existing policies in terms of facilities and equipment (WAM=3.47), faculty qualifications (WAM=3.53), and standardized program curriculum (WAM=3.51). The experienced practices and observed policies support the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program in a selected locale. Findings revealed that among experienced practices, curriculum implementation ranked highest, while professional preparation got the lowest WAM. Additionally, in terms of observed existing policies, faculty qualifications obtained the highest rating, while the facilities and equipment got the lowest rating. These results suggest that while strengths exist in curricular delivery and faculty credentials, there remain areas needing enhancement, particularly in professional preparation and facilities and equipment. Based on these findings, policy recommendations and strategic interventions are proposed, entitled

“Sustaining Physical Education Program: Policy Recommendations and Strategic Interventions for Long-Term Viability”, to sustain the BPEd program in the chosen locale.

Keywords: *Physical Education Program, Policies, Practices, Sustainability*

INTRODUCTION

Physical education, an essential component of the whole educational process, aims to develop citizens who are capable of being physically, cognitively, socially, and emotionally capable by organizing and selecting physical activities that are designed to achieve Particular outcomes (Sharma, 2022). Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) is a four-year undergraduate program offered in the 2018 curriculum that is designed to prepare future teachers who specialize in the planning and administration of instruction, assessment, and research in physical literacy. Specifically, the program aims to develop highly skilled physical education (PE) teacher-researchers with disciplinary competence in this field and allied sciences who devise curricular choices and plans that aim to achieve learners’ competency and proficiency in movement to meet their functional and health requirements. Moreover, the BPEd program is a board-licensed course designed to provide comprehensive, student-centered learning experiences, culminating in a practice teaching internship. It includes 408 hours of field study and internship, along with 2,697 hours of academic coursework. To strengthen its academic framework, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) issued Memorandum Order No. 39, Series of 2021, establishing the Policies, Standards, and Guidelines (PSGs) for the BPEd program. These cover infrastructure, faculty qualifications, curriculum alignment, and learning outcomes. General education courses like Physical Activity Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT) were also introduced to promote active lifestyles (CHED, 2013).

In basic Education, DepEd Order No. 8, Series of 2015, emphasized the role of both formative and Summative assessments in PE. However, recent developments have raised concerns about the BPEd program’s sustainability. Poor policy implementation, limited institutional resources, and declining enrollment have affected its viability. Although CHED’s PSGs aimed to enhance teaching and learning, their actual impact on student engagement and program appeal remains uncertain (Aquino, 2023). During the academic year 2024–2025, an informal interview revealed a significant decrease in BPEd enrollment at a private higher institution in Sariaya, Quezon. According to data, there were only 19 first-year students, none in the second year, 22 third-year students, and 38 fourth-year students. The fluctuating trend, dropping from 38 to 22 to none rising to 19, raises concerns about the long-term viability of the Physical Education Program in this institution. Also, this study aimed to examine the experienced practices and observed existing policies that affect the sustainability of the BPEd program in the institution. It focused on curriculum implementation, student engagement, and professional preparation, as well as facilities and equipment, faculty qualifications, and the standardized curriculum. Based on the findings, the researchers proposed policy recommendations and strategic interventions to help sustain the program in the chosen locale.

Research Questions

This study determined the experienced practices and observed existing policies that can ensure the sustainability of the BPED Program in the chosen locale.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experienced practices of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Curriculum Implementation;
 - 1.2 Student Engagement; and
 - 1.3 Professional Preparation?
2. What are the observed existing policies in the BPED program in the chosen locale in terms of:
 - 2.1 Facilities and Equipment;
 - 2.2 Faculty Qualifications; and
 - 2.3 Standardized Program Curriculum?
3. Based on the research findings, what policy recommendations and strategic interventions can be proposed by the researchers to sustain the BPED Program in the chosen locale?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To ascertain the established procedures and regulations that can guarantee the sustainability of the BPED program in the selected area, this study employed a quantitative descriptive research methodology. According to McCombes (2023), descriptive research is a methodological technique that seeks to methodically observe and record the features of a population, phenomena, or circumstances without changing any factors. It is a fundamental tool in many academic disciplines as it mostly responds to the “what,” “when,” “where,” and “how” queries rather than the “why” ones. In order to investigate the established procedures and regulations that can guarantee the BPED Program’s sustainability in the selected area, the researchers employed the descriptive technique in this study.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at one of the private higher education institutions in Sariaya, Quezon, which has experienced a decline in enrollment for the academic year 2024–2025. Despite this challenge, the school is recognized for its commitment to continuously enhancing its quality standards, particularly in the field of sports. It offers a four-year Bachelor of Physical Education (BPED) program that incorporates various experienced practices and existing policies as part of its curriculum. This study was specifically focused on BPED students, as they can provide firsthand insights into the effectiveness of experienced practices and existing policies that support the sustainability of the BPED program.

During the academic year 2024–2025, an informal interview revealed a significant decrease in BPED enrollment at a private higher institution in Sariaya, Quezon. According to data, there were only 19 first-year students, none in the second year, 22 third-year students, and 38 fourth-year students. The fluctuating trend dropping from 38 to 22 to none, then re-rising to 19, raises concerns about the long-term viability of the Physical Education Program in this institution.

In addition, there is a visible gap in the present strategy for maintaining Physical Education programs in tertiary education. Although practices and policies are present, their effects on curriculum implementation, student involvement, and program quality at large ought to be further analyzed. For this reason, the study sought to explore the existing practices and present policies that can provide the BPED Program in the selected place with sustainability.

Respondents and Sampling Technique

The respondents of this study were Bachelor of Physical Education (BPED) students currently enrolled at one private higher institution in Sariaya, Quezon, during the academic year 2024-2025. The study was focused on BPED students as they provide first-hand insights into the experienced practices and existing policies in sustaining the BPED program. The BPED program is composed of seventy-nine (79) students, particularly nineteen (19) students from the first year, zero (0) student from the second year, twenty-two (22) students from the third year, and thirty-eight (38) students from the fourth year. The researchers employed a total population sampling technique.

According to Glen (2018), Total population sampling is used when the target group is relatively small and distinguished by a unique, well-defined characteristic. This method often provides deeper and more comprehensive insights into the target population compared to partial sampling methods.

Given the relatively small population size and the distinct characteristics of the target group, total population sampling was deemed appropriate for this study. By including all 79 currently enrolled BPED students, the researchers ensured that the data reflected a comprehensive and accurate picture of the experienced practices and existing policies related to sustaining the BPED program. This approach allowed for deeper insights and minimized sampling bias, which might have occurred if only a subset of students were selected.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers followed several essential steps to gather the necessary data for this study. The researchers began the data gathering procedure by securing formal permission from the appropriate school authorities. After the validation process, the finalized questionnaire was personally distributed to the BPED student respondents. Before distribution, the researchers explained the purpose of the study and provided instructions on how to answer the survey. The respondents were given ample time to complete the questionnaire, ensuring they could provide thoughtful and accurate

responses. The researchers also explained that the identity of the respondents will remain confidential for ethical reasons.

The researchers coordinated with the respondents to schedule convenient times for answering the questionnaire, ensuring minimal disruption to their regular activities. Upon completion, the researchers collected the responses and proceeded to tally, analyze, and interpret the data using the Weighted Arithmetic Mean to determine the overall trends and insights relevant to the study objectives.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a self-made survey questionnaire to determine existing practices and policies that can ensure the sustainability of the BPED Program in the chosen locale.

According to Bondine (2022), the survey questionnaire is self-made and meant to be completed objectively by respondents. Often, it is used to collect data for quantitative research. The questionnaire consists of two parts: The first part exhibits what are the experienced practices of the respondents in terms of curriculum implementation, student engagement, and professional preparation. The second part focuses on what are the observed existing policies in the BPED program in the chosen locale in terms of facilities and equipment, faculty qualifications, and standardized program curriculum. Each variable contains ten statements, for a total of sixty statements. Likert scale to guide the respondents in rating the statements: 4 if the respondents Highly Experienced (HE), 3 if Experienced (E), 2 if Not Experienced (NE), and 1 if Highly Not Experienced (HNE). For the second part, 4 if the respondents Highly Observed (HO), 3 if Observed (O), 2 if Not Observed (NO), and 1 if Highly Not Observed (HNB).

The questionnaire used in this study undergoes a validation process to ensure its accuracy, clarity, and effectiveness. The content of the research instrument was validated by two experts in the field of Physical Education to ensure that all items are relevant and aligned with the objectives of the study. Additionally, the grammar and language used in the questionnaire statements were reviewed and validated by an English teacher to ensure linguistic correctness and clarity in both languages.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers use the following statistical treatment to analyze the data gathered precisely.

For Research Questions 1 and 2, the researchers utilized the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) to determine the experienced practices and observed existing policies in the chosen locale. The formula is shown below.

Formula:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

Where:

W = Weighted Average

n = Numbers of Terms to be Averagew_i

w_i= Corresponding Weight

X_i= Value of any particular

The researchers used 4 - Point Likert scale and interpreted the result using the continuous scale below:

For Research Question 1

Point Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 – 4.00	Highly Experienced
3	2.51 – 3.25	Experienced
2	1.76 – 2.50	Not Experienced
1	1.00 – 1.75	Highly Not Experienced

For Research Question 2

Point Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 – 4.00	Highly Observed
3	2.51 – 3.25	Observed
2	1.76 – 2.50	Not Observed
1	1.00 – 1.75	Highly Not Observed

Scope and Limitations

This study determined the experienced practices and observed existing policies for ensuring the sustainability of the Bachelor of Physical Education program. For the experienced practices, the researchers focused on curriculum implementation, student engagement, and professional preparation. On the other hand, the observed existing policies in the BPED program in the chosen locale in terms of facilities and equipment, faculty qualifications, and standardized program curriculum. The study was conducted at one of the private higher institutions in Sariaya, Quezon. The respondents of this study were first to fourth-year Bachelor of Physical Education students. To identify the

respondents of this study, a total population sampling was employed by the researchers. Moreover, the researchers utilized descriptive methods in a quantitative approach as a research design. The researchers employed and distributed a self-made survey questionnaire. Then, after two weeks of gathering data, it was analyzed and interpreted using weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) as a statistical treatment.

However, the researchers encountered various limitations during the conduct of this study. One anticipated issue has limited availability and potential lack of cooperation from respondents due to class schedules and other commitments. To address this, the researchers issued a formal request letter, reviewed by the research instructor and adviser, and duly signed by the school registrar and dean to ensure proper coordination with the institution. Following this, the researchers personally reached out to all BPED students and distributed the questionnaire during their free periods or after class hours. The researchers clearly explained the purpose and importance of the study, emphasizing how the results may benefit the BPED program. Additionally, they assured all respondents of strict confidentiality and anonymity to build trust and make participants feel more comfortable. As a proactive solution, the researchers also coordinated with instructors to possibly allocate a short time during class for answering the survey or set up designated time slots in common areas where students can respond at their convenience.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part 1. Experienced Practices

Table 1

Experienced Practices of the Respondents in terms of Curriculum Implementation

Code	Indicators	WAM	VI
1	The school curriculum follows the national educational standards and guidelines.	3.71	Highly Experienced
3	The PE subjects in the school are well-distributed across the academic years.	3.63	Highly Experienced
6	The modern teaching strategies (e.g., blended learning, technology integration) of school are incorporated into the curriculum.	3.58	Highly Experienced
5	The course content of school includes both theoretical and practical physical education activities.	3.50	Highly Experienced
8	There are school practices ensuring that students complete the required practicum and internship experiences.	3.50	Highly Experienced

10	The school supports research initiatives related to physical education and sports science.	3.50	Highly Experienced
2	The school curriculum is regularly reviewed and updated based on current educational trends.	3.47	Highly Experienced
4	The school provides sufficient instructional materials for effective curriculum implementation	3.47	Highly Experienced
7	The school curriculum includes activities promoting lifelong physical fitness and sports participation.	3.47	Highly Experienced
9	The students in the institution receive adequate exposure to coaching and officiating in different sports.	3.42	Highly Experienced
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.53	Highly Experienced

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for Verbal Interpretation were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Highly Not Experienced, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Not Experienced, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Experienced, 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Highly Experienced.

Table 1 presents the results of the experienced practices of respondents' perceptions in curriculum implementation, with an average weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.53 (Highly Experienced). The practice experienced the most in the area of curriculum implementation is the statement, school curriculum that follows the national educational standards and guidelines, which emerged as the top-rated indicator with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.71 (Highly Experienced). Also, the least experienced practice in curriculum implementation is that students in the institution receive adequate exposure to coaching and officiating in different sports, with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.42 (Highly Experienced).

This finding shows that the national educational standards and guidelines must follow the school curriculum to ensure better education. The high WAM for these indicators underscores the importance of following national educational standards and guidelines curriculum of all schools. When the schools follow those educational guidelines and standards, the students are more likely to participate in PE class, and they can enjoy it. The student receives adequate exposure to coaching and officiating in different sports from the institution, which highlights the lowest WAM suggesting that the institution need a comprehensive training to the student to have prepared them.

This aligns with the assertion of Braimoh (2017), who defines curriculum implementation as a systematic process involving learner-content interaction aimed at achieving expected outcomes. When the curriculum is grounded in national standards, it provides uniformity, quality assurance, and relevance across schools, which in turn encourages student participation and enjoyment in practical subjects like PE.

Furthermore, Syomwene (2018) emphasized that a clear mission, vision, and alignment with national goals are key indicators of effective curriculum implementation. This clarity gives students a sense of direction and enhances their engagement, particularly in skill-based subjects like Physical Education (PE).

Table 2
Experienced Practices of the Respondents in terms of Student Engagement

Code	Indicators	WAM	VI
1	As a BPED student, the institution provides activities such as academic and physical discussions.	3.61	Highly Experienced
3	There are school-organized intramurals, tournaments, and sports-related events.	3.61	Highly Experienced
6	I can engage in a community-based sports program.	3.55	Highly Experienced
2	The institution provides opportunities for students to engage in competitive and recreational sports.	3.50	Highly Experienced
8	The institution ensures that students understand the value of health and fitness by incorporating real life application.	3.50	Highly Experienced
10	The institution promotes gender equality and inclusion in sports activities.	3.47	Highly Experienced
5	I can actively participate in research or projects related to physical education and sports science.	3.45	Highly Experienced
9	I am able to apply the knowledge and skills learned in PE to maintain an active life style.	3.42	Highly Experienced
4	I have an access to well-maintained sports facilities and training equipment.	3.39	Highly Experienced
7	I am able to receive adequate support from faculty in terms of academic guidance and mentorship.	3.39	Highly Experienced
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.49	Highly Experienced

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for Verbal Interpretation were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Highly Not Experienced, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Not Experienced, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Experienced, 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Highly Experienced.

Table 2 presents the results of the respondents' perceptions of experienced practices in student engagement, with an average weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.49 (Highly Experienced). The highest rated practice in the context of student engagement is the statement, BPED students provide activities such as academic and physical discussion and school-organized intramurals, tournaments, and sports-related events with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.61 (Highly Experienced). However, the least rated indicator is that they can receive adequate support from faculty in terms of academic guidance and mentorship, with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.39 (Highly Experienced)

The findings show that BPED provides activities like academic and physical orientation, and they organize sports events. Also, to engage more of the students in physical activity, they join community sports programs. The institutions give opportunities to engage students in competitive sports. This highlights the importance of student engagement in sports programs to develop sportsmanship. Also, sometimes they are able to receive adequate academic guidance and mentorship from the faculty, which is one of the important aspects in building the student to be more productive in the future.

These findings are supported by several studies in the literature. In a systematic study, Guo et al. (2023) discovered a strong positive correlation between several aspects of students' participation in physical education, particularly behavioral and emotional involvement, and their perception of their teachers' support. It has been demonstrated that teacher support—including competence, autonomy, and emotional support—is essential for raising student interest in physical education classes. In a similar vein, Gamage et al. (2021) emphasized the beneficial effects of coaching and mentoring on student learning engagement in higher education. According to their research, mentors' capacity to offer assistance and motivation greatly improves students' academic growth and engagement. When faculty members provided them with sufficient direction and mentorship, students reported increased levels of engagement, motivation, and academic achievement.

Table 3
Experienced Practices of the Respondents in terms of Professional Preparation

Code	Indicators	WAM	VI
4	The PE program provides sufficient hands-on training (e.g., practice teaching, coaching experience, internships) that prepares students for professional careers in physical education and sports management.	3.50	Highly Experienced
1	The institution organizes comprehensive workshops and seminars to continuously enhance teachers' competence in Physical Education.	3.42	Highly Experienced
2	The physical education program prepared to adapt physical education activities for students with diverse needs and abilities.	3.42	Highly Experienced
5	BPED students received tailored instruction based on their strengths and weaknesses, ensuring equity and inclusiveness.	3.42	Highly Experienced
8	BPED students are given opportunities to participate in sports events, tournaments, or community outreach programs that improve leadership and event management skills.	3.39	Highly Experienced
9	Professional Practices Institutions provide opportunities for BPED students to engage in professional practices (e.g., practical training,	3.37	Highly Experienced

	teacher support, and continuous Improvement.		
10	Institutions often define clear graduate profiles that outline attributes such as communication skills, critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity.	3.37	Highly Experienced
3	The school implements structured programs such as regular training, workshops, mentoring, and curriculum enhancements to continuously improve the professional preparation of BPED students and faculty.	3.32	Highly Experienced
6	Students are trained on first aid and emergency and response.	3.29	Highly Experienced
7	The institution offers career guidance and job placement assistance to help BPED students transition into their professional careers.	3.24	Experienced
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.37	Highly Experienced

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for Verbal Interpretation were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Highly Not Experienced, the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Not Experienced, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Experienced, 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Highly Experienced.

Table 3 presents the result of the experienced practices of respondents' perceptions in professional preparation, with an average weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.37 (Highly Experienced). The most experienced practice in Professional Preparation is PE program that provides sufficient hands-on training (e.g., practice teaching, coaching experience, internships), preparing students for professional careers in physical education and sports management with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.50 (Highly Experienced). On the other hand, the least indicator they experienced is the statement, institutions offer career guidance and job placement assistance to help students transition into their professional careers, with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.24 (Highly Experienced).

This result shows that physical education provides hands-on training to prepare students for a professional career and sports management. It's crucial to have hands-on training to be more productive in sport and to achieve their goal. Even though the result shows that the least experienced institutions provision of guidance and assistance to help the students. As students, we need to get assistance to transform our careers in sport.

This is in line with the contention of Darling-Hammond et al. (2020), who highlighted that mixing theoretical learning with practical experience was crucial in building competency in the workplace. This mixing makes graduates ready and able to fulfill the skills and knowledge demands of their profession. In addition, Armour (2017) and Pühse & Gerber (2019) point out the significance of continuous professional

development, as it is through involvement in workshops, certifications, and collective learning communities that teachers are able to hone their skills, acquire new pedagogical approaches, and remain current with contemporary trends in physical education. The process of continuous learning is essential to sustaining high motivation, creativity, and teaching effectiveness among PE instructors.

Part II. Observed Existing Policies in the BPED Program

Table 4
Observed Existing Policies in the BPED Program in the chosen locale in Terms of Facilities and Equipment

Code	Indicators	WAM	VI
1	The institution provides well-maintained sports facilities for BPED students.	3.58	Highly Observed
5	Sports and fitness equipment are sufficient to accommodate students' needs.	3.53	Highly Observed
2	The availability of instructional materials supports effective learning in BPED courses.	3.50	Highly Observed
4	Outdoor sports areas (e.g., courts, fields) are properly maintained and meet safety standards.	3.50	Highly Observed
10	The institution allocates a sufficient budget for upgrading BPED facilities and equipment.	3.50	Highly Observed
3	Gymnasium and indoor sports facilities are accessible for practical lessons.	3.45	Highly Observed
8	Cleanliness and sanitation of PE facilities are regularly maintained.	3.45	Highly Observed
9	First-aid and emergency equipment are available in PE activity areas.	3.42	Highly Observed
7	The institution provides proper ventilation and lighting in sports facilities.	3.39	Highly Observed
6	There are dedicated storage areas for sports and PE equipment.	3.34	Highly Observed
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.47	Highly Observed

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for Verbal Interpretation were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 – 1.75 indicates Highly Not Observed, the range of 1.75 – 2.49 indicates Not Observed, the range of 2.50 – 3.24 indicates Observed, 3.25 – 4.00 indicates Highly Observed.

Table 4 presents the result of the observed existing policies in BPED program in chosen locale in terms of facilities and equipment, with an average weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.47 (Highly Experienced). Among the existing policies, the students greatly experience the statement, institution provides well-maintained sports facilities for students with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.58 (Highly Experienced). Nevertheless, the least existing policies are the dedicated storage areas for sports and PE equipment, with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.34 (Highly Experienced).

This shows that providing well-maintained facilities is essential to sports and fitness equipment to accommodate students, and instructional materials are crucial to support effective learning, like properly maintaining the safety standards of the sports area and allocating budget for upgrading the facilities and equipment for the institution. When we enhance the sports place and equipment, the students can enjoy physical activities and improve their learning in sports activities. Also, the storage areas are important to maintain all the equipment in good condition.

This finding aligns with Jaminal (2019), who emphasized that adequate and well-maintained facilities are essential factors for student learning and motivation. The presence of quality facilities not only enhances students' satisfaction but also encourages active participation in physical activities, contributing to improved learning outcomes. Furthermore, Li et al. (2022) stressed that physical education requires high standards for equipment and facilities, which are directly related to the effective implementation of PE programs and students' enthusiasm for outdoor physical exercise. Their study highlights the importance of proper management and maintenance of sports equipment and facilities to ensure safety, prolong service life, and maximize their educational value. The research also points out that dedicated personnel and clear management systems are necessary to maintain equipment integrity and prevent misuse or damage.

Table 5
Observed Existing Policies in the BPED Program in the chosen locale in Terms of Faculty Qualifications

Code	Indicators	WAM	VI
4	Teachers have sufficient teaching experience in the field of Physical Education.	3.63	Highly Observed
10	Teachers maintain professionalism and ethical standards in teaching BPED courses.	3.61	Highly Observed
5	Teachers integrate modern teaching strategies in BPED courses.	3.58	Highly Observed
6	Teachers actively engage in research related to sports and physical education.	3.53	Highly Observed
7	PE instructors demonstrate competence in handling various sports and fitness activities.	3.53	Highly Observed
9	There is a balance between theoretical and practical teaching methods used by faculty.	3.53	Highly Observed
1	BPED faculty members hold relevant degrees in Physical Education or related fields.	3.50	Highly Observed
3	Teachers possess national certifications or licenses related to sports and fitness.	3.50	Highly Observed
8	The institution ensures that BPED faculty members meet the required teaching standards.	3.50	Highly Observed
2	Teachers regularly attend training, seminars, and workshops on PE instruction.	3.34	Highly Observed
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.53	Highly Observed

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for Verbal Interpretation were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 – 1.75 indicates Highly Not Observed, the range of 1.75 – 2.49 indicates Not Observed, the range of 2.50 – 3.24 indicates Observed, 3.25 – 4.00 indicates Highly Observed.

Table 5 presents the result of the observed existing policies in BPED program in chosen locale in terms of the Faculty orientation, with an average weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.53 (Highly Experienced). The highly experienced policy in the program is the statement, teachers who have sufficient teaching experience in the field of PE with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.63 (Highly Experienced). However, the least experienced policy in the program in student observation is that teachers regularly attend training, seminars, and workshops on PE instruction with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.34 (Highly Experienced).

It reveals that teachers with enough teaching experience, professional development and who integrate modern strategies in teaching are key to attracting students to participate in physical education. The importance of professional teaching has a great impact on the development of their skills. With the help of modern strategies, students can learn better and engage in physical activities. Also, regular attendance at events is enough to gain new knowledge in physical education.

This finding is supported by Munna and Kalam (2021), who emphasized that effective teaching is characterized by strong organization, communication, motivation, and human relations skills. These components are essential for maximizing learning opportunities and ensuring student success, regardless of the subject or setting. Furthermore, the literature states that physical educators should be graduates of approved training institutions and possess robust health to serve as role models for their students (“Qualification and Qualities of a Good Physical Education Teacher,” n.d.). The presence of qualified and experienced teachers not only enhances the quality of instruction but also motivates students to actively participate in physical activities, contributing to their overall development and performance. On the other hand, the study of Jung et al. (2022) highlights the significance of ongoing professional development for PE teachers. The study suggests that providing faculty with professional development opportunities is essential for updating teaching practices, integrating modern strategies, and supporting curricular priorities such as skill development and health promotion. Regular participation in training and workshops allows teachers to stay informed about current trends and best practices, ultimately benefiting student learning and engagement.

Table 6
Observed Existing Policies in the BPED Program in the chosen locale in Terms of Standardized Program Curriculum

Code	Indicators	WAM	VI
6	Courses integrate modern technology and digital tools for PE instruction.	3.58	Highly Observed
2	The course offerings provide a balance between theory and practical application.	3.53	Highly Observed

3	The program includes subjects that cater to various aspects of physical education (e.g., coaching, sports science, fitness management).	3.53	Highly Observed
5	The curriculum includes internship and field experience for students.	3.53	Highly Observed
8	The curriculum includes adaptive physical education for students with special needs.	3.53	Highly Observed
1	The BPED curriculum aligns with the national and institutional educational standards.	3.50	Highly Observed
10	The curriculum promotes lifelong learning and professional growth in the field of Physical Education.	3.50	Highly Observed
7	The institution provides elective courses that expand students' career opportunities in PE.	3.47	Highly Observed
4	The institution regularly updates the curriculum based on new trends and policies in PE.	3.45	Highly Observed
9	BPED students undergo regular assessment to evaluate their competencies in PE-related skills.	3.45	Highly Observed
Average Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.51	Highly Observed

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for Verbal Interpretation were used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 – 1.75 indicates Highly Not Observed, the range of 1.75 – 2.49 indicates Not Observed, the range of 2.50 – 3.24 indicates Observed, 3.25 – 4.00 indicates Highly Observed.

Table 6 presents the results of the observed existing policies in the BPED program in the chosen locale in terms of Standardized Program Curriculum, with an average weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.51 (Highly Experienced). The most experienced policy in the program is that statement, courses that integrate modern technology and digital tools for instruction, with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.58 (Highly Experienced). Also, the least existing policies in the program in student observation are institutions that regularly update the curriculum based on new trends and policies, and students undergo regular assessment to evaluate their competencies in PE-related skills and with a weighted arithmetic mean (WAM) of 3.45 (Highly Experienced).

This highlights that BPED curriculum is designed to provide a well-rounded education in physical education, integrating modern technology and digital tools into instruction, balancing theoretical knowledge with practical applications, and offering subjects that cover various aspects of physical education, including coaching, sports science, and fitness management. This also includes internships and field experiences to enhance students' hands-on learning with adaptive physical education courses to support those with special needs. Also, national and institutional educational standards, the curriculum provides lifelong learning and professional growth, ensuring graduates are well-prepared for careers in physical education.

This aligns with the findings of Dudley and Burden (2019), who highlighted that a well-structured curriculum, supported by standardized guidelines and the integration of technology, can positively impact student learning across cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Their meta-analysis affirmed that allocating sufficient curriculum time to PE, while incorporating modern instructional tools, supports comprehensive student development without negatively affecting academic achievement in other areas.

Part III. Output of the Study

The actual output of this study is policy recommendations and strategic interventions aimed at sustaining the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program in the chosen locale. Grounded in the research findings, these outputs address the root causes of declining enrollment and student engagement. The policy recommendations focus on enhancing institutional support, improving curriculum relevance, and strengthening stakeholder partnerships, while the strategic interventions include faculty development programs, student mentoring systems, promotional campaigns, and career-oriented activities. Together, these initiatives are designed to make the BPEd program more attractive, effective, and sustainable over the long term.

Conclusions

The study's findings have led the present researchers to the following conclusion. After analyzing the data, the current researchers arrived at the following conclusions.

1. The respondents demonstrated a high level of experience in curriculum implementation, student engagement, and professional preparation, as reflected by their weighted average means, all falling under the Highly Experienced category.
2. The existing policies of the BPEd program in the chosen local covering facilities and equipment, faculty qualifications, and the standardized curriculum were all rated as Highly Experienced, indicating strong policy implementation and institutional support.
3. In light of the findings, the researchers emphasize the importance of implementing the proposed plan titled "*Sustaining Physical Education Program: Policy Recommendations and Strategic Interventions for Long-Term Viability.*" This plan is designed to enhance student learning and development, support teachers through effective strategies and resources, and assist administrators in strengthening the program. It also provides a framework for improving the accessibility and relevance of Physical Education, while serving as a valuable reference for future research on sustaining program quality.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Students enhance participation in Physical Education activities by encouraging active engagement and awareness of the long-term benefits of physical fitness.

Students may also be provided with varied and inclusive learning experiences to further enrich their development.

2. Teachers may continuously pursue professional growth through training, seminars, and workshops aligned with current trends in Physical Education. This may help maintain high-quality instruction and sustain their level of expertise in curriculum implementation, student engagement, and professional preparation.

3. School Administrators strengthen institutional support by investing in updated facilities and equipment, ensuring qualified teaching staff, and regularly reviewing and enhancing the BPEd curriculum to meet evolving educational needs and standards.

4. It is also recommended to consider this program Improvement proposed plan, *“Sustaining Physical Education Program: Policy Recommendations and Strategic Interventions for Long-Term Viability,”* which may be implemented to ensure the continuous development and relevance of the BPEd program. Regular program evaluation and stakeholder feedback should be conducted to identify areas for further improvement.

5. Educational Institutions are encouraged to adopt the study’s recommendations as a guide in policy formation and resource allocation to improve Physical Education accessibility and effectiveness, especially in resource-limited settings.

6. Parallel Studies may be conducted in other regions or institutions to compare findings and gain broader insights into the effectiveness of BPEd programs across different contexts.

7. Future researchers may replicate this study to validate the results or expand its scope by exploring other variables or implementing the proposed interventions. This will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of sustaining quality Physical Education programs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that this study complied with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and participation was voluntary with the right to withdraw at any time. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, and data privacy protocols were observed throughout the study. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded, and no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the research. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes. Any use of artificial intelligence tools was limited to language editing and formatting assistance, with full responsibility for the content retained by the authors.

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